

Sustainability Requirements Engineering Model: Systematic Mapping Review

Abstract—The need for sustainability in software engineering has become increasingly important as society and businesses focus on social, economic and environmental responsibility. Sustainable software engineering aims to reduce the environmental impact of software throughout its lifecycle, from design to disposal. Requirements engineering is a critical aspect of sustainable software engineering, as it provides a means for explicitly incorporating sustainability requirements into software development processes.

In this article, we present a systematic mapping review of the literature on model-based approaches to conceptual sustainability software requirements engineering. We conducted a comprehensive search of major scientific databases. Our mapping review aims to identify the state-of-the-art in modeling conceptual sustainability requirements in software engineering, and to provide insights into the challenges and opportunities in this area.

Index Terms—requirements engineering, modeling conceptual, sustainability engineering, systematic mapping

I. INTRODUCTION

In recent times, considering sustainability has become a vital factor in conducting business. If a company fails to uphold sustainable practices, it may face significant public criticism and risk losing its market [2].

To establish the scope of our research, it is important to define our understanding of sustainability and how it relates to software engineering. The most widely accepted definition of sustainable development, as cited in [3], “is the ability to meet the needs of the present without compromising the ability of future generations to meet their own needs”. This definition emphasizes the importance of satisfying the requirements of society, economy, and environment, which are the three primary dimensions of sustainability.

The initial stage of software engineering, known as Requirements Engineering (RE), involves determining the precise scope of the system and gradually expanding on the needs and concerns of stakeholders [1].

Brito et al [10] say “The requirements engineering process can contribute to the sustainability of software system development by understanding the organizational goals, identifying stakeholder needs, eliciting requirements, finding metrics to assess realization of the requirements, and evaluating the system’s sustainability. During this process, the participation of the systems’ stakeholders is fundamental”.

One of the key challenges in RE for sustainability is the conceptualization of sustainability requirements. Sustainability requirements are often complex, multifaceted, and context-dependent, making them difficult to capture and integrate into software engineering processes [9]. Model-based approaches can help to address this challenge by providing a means for conceptualizing and modeling sustainability requirements.

Our study builds on the findings of our earlier work and utilizes a larger dataset to draw more robust conclusions. Our research objective is to provide an updated overview of the current state of research on requirements engineering for sustainability.

Our contribution is a systematic mapping study, following the guidelines outlined in [6]. We have developed more comprehensive research questions, used an adapted search string, and included a wider range of publication channels. Through this study, we aim to identify what exists related to my research questions and too identify trends, gaps, and challenges in the field of requirements engineering for sustainability and provide insights for future research. The results of this study are expected to be useful for interested in the integration of sustainability into requirements engineering practices.

II. BACKGROUND

A. Requirements Engineering for Sustainability

Sustainability focuses on meeting the needs of the present without compromising the ability of future generations to meet their needs [11]. The given definition emphasizes the significance of sustainability, highlighting the need for conscious actions to create a better world for future generations. However, addressing sustainability is not a simple task due to its complexity. Consequently, comprehensive measures must be implemented on both global and individual levels to overcome the obstacles and challenges associated with sustainability. Only through collective efforts can we work towards achieving the ultimate goal of global sustainability [16].

The overarching objective of sustainable development is to ensure the habitability of the Earth for future generations. As stated in [17], sustainable development rests upon three interconnected and mutually reinforcing pillars: economic development, social development, and environmental protection. These pillars work in harmony to promote a balanced and sustainable approach to development, encompassing the well-being of society, the preservation of the environment, and the advancement of economic prosperity.

Goodland [18] defines the fundamental dimensions for a comprehensive sustainability analysis as social, economic, and environmental. These dimensions align with the UN definition of sustainable development [3], which also emphasizes the importance of considering these three dimensions. However, when examining technical systems, including software systems, these four dimensions alone may not adequately address the long-term evolution and suitability for extended use. Therefore, it is necessary to introduce technical sustainability as an

additional dimension to account for the specific requirements and considerations related to the sustainability of (software) systems.

The Software Sustainability Institute define sustainability as “software you use today will be available - and continue to be improved and supported - in the future” [14].

There has been a growing recognition of sustainable software development, with an expanding range of definitions focusing on sustainability from a software development perspective. According to Amsel et al. [15], sustainable software engineering is a process that strives to develop dependable and durable software that meets user needs while simultaneously minimizing environmental impacts. This definition highlights the dual objectives of creating software that is both user-centric and environmentally conscious.

The concept of Requirements Engineering for Sustainability (RE4S) [4] involves utilizing sustainable development techniques in conjunction with requirements engineering to enhance the ecological, societal, and economic sustainability of software systems, as well as their direct and indirect impact on the surrounding business and operational context.

By integrating sustainability into the RE process, software engineers can ensure that software systems are designed to meet the needs of society and the environment, as well as the demands of the market [4].

The dimensions of sustainability that we take into consideration [7] are as follows:

- *Human/individual sustainability*: It involves maintaining human capital, such as health, education, happiness, etc., throughout an individual’s lifetime. In the context of software systems, this dimension is specifically relevant for analyzing the impact on both users and developers. Individual sustainability also referred to as personal sustainability [22].
- *Social sustainability*: It involves preserving social capital, services, and communities to maintain solidarity in society. Analyzing this aspect is crucial for software systems in relation to their impact on user communities. Social sustainability revolves around safeguarding the interests of social communities, groups of individuals, or organizations [24].
- *Economic sustainability*: It pertains to the maintenance of assets in the form of capital or added value, which concerns software developers, be it companies or those involved in free open source initiatives. Economic sustainability prioritizes stakeholders’ long-term investments and maximizing return on investment [23].
- *Environmental sustainability*: It involves preserving and protecting the environment while utilizing its resources, which every software system does directly (in terms of energy consumption) or indirectly (in terms of resource usage and application environment). The primary focus is on safeguarding natural resources, such as energy and air, among others [21], [22].
- *Technical sustainability*: It focuses on improving and maintaining the longevity of systems within a rapidly

changing technological environment. Technical sustainability is connected to software maintenance, flexibility, evolution, and the ease of transitions [20].

Fig. 1. Dimensions of sustainability in sustainable software engineering [24]

Figure 1 represents and summarizes the dimensions of sustainable software engineering along with their main objectives. The significance and importance of sustainability and sustainable software engineering, as well as its various dimensions, have been emphasized by researchers [24].

B. Systematic Mapping Review

As highlighted in [8], when a research area reaches a certain level of maturity, there is typically a significant rise in the quantity of reports and findings being disseminated. Consequently, it becomes crucial to compile and present comprehensive summaries and overviews of the research in order to facilitate a better understanding of the field. This enables researchers and practitioners to navigate through the wealth of information available and gain valuable insights from the collective body of knowledge.

Considering the nature of the topic, a systematic mapping study was conducted in reference to the guidelines according to Petersen et al. [8], which has the steps: definition of research questions, conducting the search for relevant papers, screening of papers, keywording of abstracts and data extraction and mapping (see Figure 2). In the sections that follow, the research questions (RQs) are described and the correlating metrics for this study is presented.

In our study, we employ the systematic mapping study approach as outlined in [8] to offer a comprehensive overview of the current research in sustainable software engineering. We classify the research based on different aspects, including the field of sustainability, type of research, and specific aspects being addressed. Through these classifications, we create mappings that enable us to identify areas of interest and also highlight aspects of sustainability that may have received limited attention [19]. This approach allows us to gain insights into the existing body of knowledge in sustainable software engineering, identify research gaps, and shed light on areas that require further exploration and investigation.

Fig. 2. The Systematic Mapping Process

III. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The focus of this study is to outline the “state of the art” of Requirements Engineering for Sustainability. Thus, the proposal main research question for this study is:

What are the existing modeling, ontology, taxonomy or modeling languages for sustainability requirements?

Our research question has been divided into three research question. In order to better achieve the objectives of the systematic mapping study.

A. Research questions

- *RQ1*: What are the existing conceptual models for sustainability requirements engineering?
- *RQ2*: What are the specific domain languages that describe sustainability requirements?
- *RQ3*: What taxonomies/ontologies exist for sustainability?

B. Search Strategy

This section presents the search strategy used to gather relevant literature on the topic. The authors utilized the most prominent academic databases in the fields of computer science and information systems, including:

- ACM (<http://dl.acm.org>)
- DBLP (<http://dblp.org/>)
- IEEE Xplorer (<http://ieeexplore.ieee.org/>)

To develop an effective search string and keywords, the authors experimented with various combinations of search strings across different databases and ultimately arrived at the following for the final search:

(sustainability) AND (model*) AND (requirements OR software engineering OR ontology OR taxonomy OR analysis OR goal OR conceptual)

C. Search Execution

We conducted a search on the previously mentioned databases using the search string to look for relevant literature. The search was carried out on the metadata fields such as title, abstract, and keywords. We selected results based on their relevance to the search string. We obtained the complete citation and abstract information as well as the full texts of the retrieved articles. To avoid redundancy, we removed duplicates from the results. We saved the original sources in a Google Drive folder.

D. Study Selection

The purpose of the selection process was to determine which articles are most pertinent to the objective of this mapping study. In cases where the same paper was found in multiple sources, it was included only once in accordance with our search criteria.

In order to avoid researcher subjectivity, we chose the following exclusion criteria:

- *Based on accessibility*: Based on accessibility: Libraries that NOVA University Lisbon does not have access to.
- *Based on language*: Papers that are not written in or translated into English.
- *Based on titles and abstract*: The title does not indicate any relation to modeling or ontology or taxonomy in RE for sustainability.
- *Based on full text*: The content is not relevant to the RQs.

E. Data extraction

This section presents the results from the Study Selection section 3.D. Out of a total of 850, publication dates shows that there is a majority of papers in the range of 1997 to 2023 with a peak in 2020.

IV. RESULTS

A. Temporal Distribution

Fig. 3 shows the non-exclusive distribution per year of the 850 publications. We observed one trend in the publication count over the years. Starting from 2020 there is a surge in the number of papers in all digital libraries. Furthermore, a large portion of the selected papers, 431 exactly were retrieved from IEEE Xplorer.

Fig. 3. Temporal Distribution

Between 1997 and 2014, the published papers account yearly for less than 25% of the total number of selected publications. More than 50% publications selected is above 2019. An important aspect we take into account in the remainder of the data analysis is that the decrease from 2023 might be because the set of papers from 2023 is incomplete.

The the estimate is that the next four years will grow at the same pace, because the year is not over yet, and many events have yet to occur.

B. Search Classification

After filtering the papers based on title and abstract, 27 papers were singled out for full-text reading. This resulted in 11 articles (See table I). Then they were categorized to answer the RQs, presented in section 4.C.

It is important to highlight that the 11 final articles were published between 2013 and 2022, it shows how recent this research topic is.

Total	Drop Duplicates	Title and Abstract	Full Text
850	712	27	11

TABLE I
FILTER ARTICLES.

C. Data Analysis

The result from the study consists of three aspects and twelve characteristics (refer to table II, III, IV). Each of the 11 articles reviewed in the systematic mapping review can be described by one or more of these characteristics. The following three dimensions were derived:

- **Representation:** This aspect encompasses different modes of representing sustainability, including graphical representations that utilize visual elements to depict sustainability in process models, textual descriptions that rely on text-based explanations, and mathematical approaches that incorporate metrics and formulas.
- **Modeling technique:** This dimension focuses on the specific modeling notations employed, such as OWL, i*, UML, and other relevant notations. It does not necessarily involve designing or redesigning a notation, but rather demonstrates how calculations and modeling operations are performed.
- **Dimensions Sustainability:** This dimension differentiates between the economic, environmental, social, individual and technical dimensions of sustainability, considering their distinct aspects and implications.

As depicted in Table II, the findings indicate that only one article utilized textual representation to describe the model, while the remaining articles employed graphical representation to depict sustainability-related concepts. None of the articles made use of mathematical representation.

The analysis of the data presented in Table III clearly indicates that a significant number of articles use modeling techniques like OWL, UML and i* (63%), to describe these sustainability concepts in software engineering and requirements engineering. But only OWL is a language specifically developed for the Semantic Web, aiming to represent intricate and extensive knowledge about entities, collections of entities, and their interrelationships [36].

Articles	Representation		
	Textual	graphical	Mathematical
[25]		X	
[26]		X	
[27]	X		
[28]		X	
[29]		X	
[30]		X	
[31]		X	
[32]		X	
[33]		X	
[34]		X	
[35]		X	

TABLE II
MODES OF REPRESENTING SUSTAINABILITY.

The other 27% only one article ([31]) use XML nets, which provides rules for defining any data or uses diagrams to represent specific sustainability concepts.

Articles	Modeling Technique			
	OWL	UML	i*	Others
[25]	X	X		
[26]	X			
[27]				
[28]			X	
[29]			X	
[30]				X
[31]	X			
[32]				X
[33]			X	
[34]				X
[35]				X

TABLE III
MODELING TECHNIQUE OF REPRESENTING SUSTAINABILITY.

Articles	Dimensions Sustainability				
	Economic	Environmental	Social	Individual	Technical
[25]	X	X	X	X	X
[26]	X	X	X		
[27]	X	X	X		
[28]	X	X	X	X	X
[29]				X	
[30]	X	X	X		
[31]			X		
[32]	X	X	X		
[33]	X	X	X		
[34]		X			
[35]	X	X	X		

TABLE IV
DIMENSIONS OF SUSTAINABILITY.

According to the results presented in Table IV, it is evident that a limited proportion of the articles comprehensively address the five dimensions of sustainability, with only 18% of them fully addressing. On the other hand, the majority of articles (82%) incorporate the environmental, economic, and social dimensions, which are the three foundations of sustainability. However, a smaller percentage of articles (27%) focus solely on one dimension of sustainability.

Types of Venues	Publications
Journal	[25], [26], [30]
Conference	[34], [31], [32], [27]
Workshop	[29], [33], [28]
Book publisher	[35]

TABLE V
TYPES OF VENUES PER PUBLICATIONS.

The table V provides an overview of the most common and relevant types of publication venues in the field of Requirements Engineering for Sustainability. There is a balance in terms of publication venues, with conferences being prominently featured in the field.

The articles [29] and [28] stand out for being published in Workshops of field, Requirements Engineering Workshop and iStar Workshop respectively.

The next subsection provides an overview of all the RQs with a discussion to determine if the articles comply with the objective of this study.

1) *RQ1: What are the existing conceptual models for sustainability requirements engineering?* : Some of the prominent conceptual models in this field include:

OntoSUSD: The OntoSUSD is created through the application of a practical ontology engineering methodology, which involves the reuse of relevant ontologies [25]. This model encompasses requirements engineering, with reuse others model with a good domain coverage.

GRL for Representing the Sustainability Reference Model: Uses Goal-oriented Requirement Language (GRL) that allows for reasoning with qualitative and quantitative data. In its new form, the reference model is more accessible (due to a better know notation) and provides more means for guidance and analysis [28].

These conceptual models of our mapping, offer valuable guidance for integrating sustainability into requirements engineering practices.

It is important to highlight that these two models describe the five dimensions of sustainability.

2) *RQ2: What are the specific domain languages that describe sustainability requirements?*: Our mapping did not find any articles with specific domain languages that describe sustainability requirements.

3) *RQ3: What taxonomies/ontologies exist for sustainability?*: Our mapping find four articles for this question. Here are some examples of articles that discuss taxonomies and ontologies for sustainability:

“OntoSUSD: Software engineering approaches integration ontology for sustainable software development” [25] discusses

a ontology that cover five dimensions of sustainability and using UML for representation of ontology and same ontology for system using OWL.

“An ontology-based knowledge modelling for a sustainability assessment domain” [26] presents ontology addressed compound problem the selection of a sustainability assessment approach using OWL and cover three bases dimensions of sustainability.

“Sustainability in Business Process Models: A Taxonomy-Driven Approach to Synthesize Knowledge and Structure the Field”. proposes an taxonomy of sustainability in process models, a verification of current deficits [27], described in a textual manner.

“Domain Ontology of Social Sustainable Development” [31] proposed as a part of the ontological metamodel of SSustainable Development in OWL, covering only the social dimension

These articles provide insights into the development and application of taxonomies and ontologies for sustainability, highlighting the importance of structured and standardized frameworks for addressing sustainability challenges.

V. CONCLUSION

In this paper, we conducted a systematic mapping study to present a comprehensive overview of the existing knowledge and research in the field of RE for sustainability conceptual model. To achieve this objective, we formulated three research questions (RQ 1-3) that focused on various research topics.

this systematic mapping review has provided a overview of the current state of research on sustainability requirements engineering conceptual models. Through a mapping study of a wide range of literature sources.

The synthesis of results presented in visual graphics and tables, along with the concise compilation of included publications, provides a condensed overview of the Sustainability Requirements Engineering Conceptual Model field. It is evident that RE for sustainability has emerged as a prominent area of research.

Given the increasing importance of RE for sustainability and the extensive research conducted thus far, we emphasize the need for a future roadmap that identifies critical research gaps and proposes potential avenues to address them. Such a roadmap would serve as a valuable guide for future research endeavors, highlighting areas where further investigation is warranted and outlining promising approaches to bridge these gaps.

By developing a comprehensive roadmap, the research community can foster collaboration and prioritize efforts to advance the field Requirements Engineering Conceptual Model for Sustainability. This strategic approach will contribute to the development of innovative solutions and promote the integration of sustainability principles into requirements engineering practices.

REFERENCES

- [1] Zave, Pamela. "Classification of research efforts in requirements engineering." ACM Computing Surveys (CSUR) 29.4 (1997): 315-321.

- [2] Du W, Pan SL, Zuo M. How to balance sustainability and profitability in technology organizations: An ambidextrous perspective. *IEEE Transactions on Engineering Management*. 2013;60(2):366-385
- [3] Imperatives, Strategic. "Report of the World Commission on Environment and Development: Our common future." Accessed Feb 10 (1987): 1-300.
- [4] Birgit Penzenstadler, Bill Tomlinson, and Debra Richardson. Re4s: Support environmental sustainability by requirements engineering. In *International Workshop on Requirements Engineering for Sustainable Systems*, 2012.
- [5] Penzenstadler, B., Raturi, A., Richardson, D., Calero, C., Femmer, H., Franch, X.: Systematic Mapping Study on Software Engineering for Sustainability (SE4S). In: *Proceedings of the 18th International Conference on Evaluation and Assessment in Software Engineering*. p. 14:1–14:14. ACM, New York, NY, USA (2014).
- [6] Petersen, K., Vakkalanka, S., Kuzniarz, L.: Guidelines for conducting systematic mapping studies in software engineering: An update. *Inf. Softw. Technol.* 64, 1–18 (2015).
- [7] Birgit Penzenstadler and Henning Femmer. A Generic Model for Sustainability with Process- and Product-specific Instances. In *First Intl. Workshop on Green In Software Engineering and Green By Software Engineering*, 2013.
- [8] Petersen, Kai, et al. "Systematic mapping studies in software engineering." *12th International Conference on Evaluation and Assessment in Software Engineering (EASE)* 12. 2008.
- [9] Saputri, Theresia Ratih Dewi, and Seok-Won Lee. "Incorporating sustainability design in requirements engineering process: A preliminary study." *Requirements Engineering Toward Sustainable World: Third Asia-Pacific Symposium, APRES 2016, Nagoya, Japan, November 10-12, 2016, Proceedings 3*. Springer Singapore, 2016.
- [10] Brito, I. S., Conejero, J. M., Moreira, A., Araújo, J. (2018, May). A concern-oriented sustainability approach. In *2018 12th international conference on research challenges in information science (RCIS)* (pp. 1-12). IEEE.
- [11] What is sustainability. url: <http://www.globalfootprints.org/sustainability/> (visited on 2023).
- [12] Becker, C., Chitchyan, R., Duboc, L., Easterbrook, S., Penzenstadler, B., Seyff, N., Venters, C. C. (2015, May). Sustainability design and software: The karlskrona manifesto. In *2015 IEEE/ACM 37th IEEE International Conference on Software Engineering (Vol. 2, pp. 467-476)*. IEEE.
- [13] The Five Dimensions of Sustainable Software Engineering and How Education Can Help!. url: <https://luisacruz.github.io/2022/01/01/sustainable-se-intro> (visited on 2023).
- [14] Software Sustainability Institute. Available: <http://www.software.ac.uk/about>.
- [15] N. Amsel, Z. Ibrahim, A. Malik, B. Tomlinson. "Toward sustainable software engineering," *ICSE: Proceedings of the 33rd International Conference on Software*
- [16] Albuquerque, D. H. (2020). *An Approach Regarding Sustainability Requirements for Sustainable Software Development* (Master dissertation).
- [17] W. M. Adams. *The Future of Sustainability Re-thinking Environment and Development in the Twenty-first Century*. Technical report, IUCN, June 2006.
- [18] R. Goodland. *Encyclopedia of Global Environmental Change, chapter Sustainability: Human, Social, Economic and Environmental*. Wiley and Sons, 2002.
- [19] D. Budgen, M. Turner, P. Brereton, and B. Kitchenham. Using mapping studies in software engineering. In J. Buckley, J. Rooksby, and R. Bednarik, editors, *Proceedings of the 20th Annual Meeting of the Psychology of Programming Interest Group*, volume 2008, pages 195–204, 2008.
- [20] R. Chitchyan, L. Duboc, C. Becker, S. Betz, B. Penzenstadler, and C. C. Venters, "Sustainability Design in Requirements Engineering: State of Practice," in *2016 IEEE/ACM 38th IEEE International Conference on Software Engineering Companion Sustain*, 2016, pp. 533–542.
- [21] S. Naumann, E. Kern, M. Dick, and T. Johann, "Sustainable Software Engineering: Process and Quality Models, Life Cycle, and Social Aspects," *ICT Innov. Sustain. Adv. Intell. Syst. Comput.*, vol. 310, pp. 191–205, 2015.
- [22] R. Chitchyan, I. Groher, and J. Noppen, "Uncovering sustainability concerns in software product lines," *J. Softw. Evol. Process*, vol. 29, no. 2, pp. 1–20, 2017.
- [23] B. Penzenstadler et al., "Software Engineering for Sustainability: Find the Leverage Points!," *IEEE Softw.*, vol. 35, no. 4, pp. 22–33, 2018
- [24] Nazir, S., et al. "Sustainable Software Engineering: A Perspective of Individual Sustainability Challenges." *11th Malaysian Software Engineering Conference (MySEC)*. 2018.
- [25] Zada, Islam, et al. "OntoSuSD: Software engineering approaches integration ontology for sustainable software development." *Software: Practice and Experience* 53.2 (2023): 283-317.
- [26] Konys, Agnieszka. "An ontology-based knowledge modelling for a sustainability assessment domain." *Sustainability* 10.2 (2018): 300
- [27] Schoormann, Thorsten, Dennis Behrens, and Ralf Knackstedt. "Sustainability in Business Process Models: A Taxonomy-Driven Approach to Synthesize Knowledge and Structure the Field." *ICIS*. 2017.
- [28] Penzenstadler, Birgit. "GRL for Representing the Sustainability Reference Model." *iStar*. 2015.
- [29] Mussbacher, Gunter, and Douglas Nuttall. "Goal modeling for sustainability: The case of time." *2014 IEEE 4th International Model-Driven Requirements Engineering Workshop (MoDRE)*. IEEE, 2014.
- [30] Chowdhury, Gobinda. "Sustainability of digital libraries: A conceptual model and a research framework." *International Journal on Digital Libraries* 14 (2014): 181-195.
- [31] Ivanova, Adelina, Boryana Deliyanska, and Vladislav Todorov. "Domain ontology of social sustainable development." *AIP Conference Proceedings*. Vol. 2333, No. 1. AIP Publishing LLC, 2021.
- [32] Chowdhury, Gobinda G. "Sustainability of digital libraries: A conceptual model." *Research and Advanced Technology for Digital Libraries: International Conference on Theory and Practice of Digital Libraries, TPDL 2013, Valletta, Malta, September 22-26, 2013, Proceedings 3*. Springer Berlin Heidelberg, 2013.
- [33] Penzenstadler, Birgit, and Henning Femmer. "A generic model for sustainability with process-and product-specific instances." *Proceedings of the 2013 workshop on Green in/by software engineering*. 2013.
- [34] Betz, Stefanie. "Sustainability aware process management using xml-nets." *Proceeding of the 28th EnviroInfo Conference*. 2014.
- [35] Muthu, Mohankumar, K. Banuroopa, and S. Arunadevi. "Green and Sustainability in Software Development Lifecycle Process." *Sustainability Assessment at the 21st century* 27.63 (2019).
- [36] Web Ontology Language (OWL): <https://www.w3.org/OWL/>.